

VALIDATION OF THE DEVELOPED OPEN SOURCE LIBRARY FOR FAR-FIELD NOISE PREDICTION

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The paper is focused on the validation of the developed open-source library libAcoustics for the far-field noise prediction by means of integral acoustic analogy. The library uses OpenFOAM for the near-field flow calculation and is available online at GitHub. Two benchmark cases with different formulations for computing the Ffowcs Williams and Hawkings equation are considered. In the first one, the spectrum of the acoustic noise generated by a rod-airfoil configuration is investigated. The near-field is calculated using large eddy simulation with a low-dissipation scheme, the far-field noise is predicted by a formulation based on the Garrick triangle. In the second case, acoustic perturbations generated by the compressible jet at a low Reynolds number are analyzed. Acoustic noise calculations are performed for the jet with Mach 0.9 and Reynolds number 3600 using Farassat 1A formulation. The obtained time-averaged and pulsating flow parameters and far-field noise have been compared with the available experimental data. The results of numerical simulations show a good agreement with the reference data. Thus, the developed library exhibits the potential for solving a wide range of computational aeroacoustics problems.

Keywords: rod-airfoil, jet, aeroacoustics, OpenFOAM, libAcoustics.

1. Introduction

Currently, one of the main approaches used to model acoustic wave propagation is the solution of the Ffowcs Williams and Hawkings (FW-H) equation. In [1] the authors extended the range of applicability of the Lighthill's equation for turbulent jets when it is necessary to take into account the noise generated by walls. The derivations may be drawn for multipole decomposition of the wave equation solution for different variants of the initial problem formulation: for a fixed surface (then the FW-H equation is transformed into the Curle equation), for a movable rigid and deformable surface, for a permeable surface that closes a half-space with an acoustic wall emitting waves, in the case when the observer or FW-H surface move together or separately. Detailed analysis of the multipole decomposition of the FW-H equation from the side of specific applications was discussed in [1,2]. Ffowcs Williams and Hawkings also pointed out the main ways to transform the general equation, which has differentials in space of the observer coordinates system, into differentials in time in the coordinates system of the source or the observer.

Now the majority of the industrial problems devoted to the research of noise generation and distribution are solved by hybrid approaches. The given approaches are based on the separate calculation of sources of noise (near-field), for example, with use of a finite volume method and eddy-resolve approaches, and their propagation with an application of integral methods. As a rule, such methods are implemented in commercial software packages, which limits their use in scientific and applied research. The alternative is to use open-source packages. The OpenFOAM is well proved the decision of complex industrial problems and at present allows to implement wide enough possibilities for complication of

mathematical models and increase in the scale of described problems. In [3] the authors described the main idea of implementing the libAcoustics library for calculating acoustic pressure in the far field using the Curle analogy. At present, an extensive modification of this library has been carried out, which allows to significantly expand the application of the open-source package OpenFOAM for research in the field of computational aeroacoustics.

2. Computational algorithm

The finite volume method implemented in the OpenFOAM package has been used for numerical simulation of physical processes occurring in the near field which lead to sound pressure pulsations. The developed library is at the post-processing level towards the basic OpenFOAM solvers. However, the way of library realization allows it to work together with the solver in a mode of the connected dynamic library (functionObject API) using data from solutions in real time. In the process of calculation of pressure, velocity and density fields generated by turbulent flow are stored on the selected surface and then acoustic pressure in the far-field is calculated according to the integral formulation of Ffowcs Williams and Hawkings equation solution.

The basic equations implemented in the library for various integral formulations are described in detail in [4]. Disregarding the volume source, the acoustic pressure in the integral form can be presented as follows:

$$p'(x,t) = p'_T(x,t) + p'_L(x,t), \quad (1)$$

where $p'_T(x,t)$ and $p'_L(x,t)$ are integral terms correspond to the thickness and loading components [4].

Methods for calculating the FW-H integral are divided into integrals in the coordinate system of the source's time and retarded time [5,6]. For its part $p'_T(x,t)$ и $p'_L(x,t)$ are determined according to the formulation chosen. Thus, the Farassat 1A formulation is used to determine the noise in the far field generated by an acoustic source moving in the air [7]. This formulation is widely used to calculate the acoustic pressure from the rotor or jet flows. The approach based on the Garrick triangle (GT formulation) is typically applied when both the source and observer are stationary and in a homogeneous flow, for example, when conducting wind tunnel tests [8]. One of the two implemented formulations is chosen depending on the task which is solved. Both approaches are used to calculate the permeable surface surrounding the surface emitter of acoustic waves. The following formula is used to calculate the sound pressure level (SPL):

$$SPL = 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{p_{rms}}{p_{ref}} \right), \quad (2)$$

where p_{rms} is the root mean square sound pressure, p_{ref} is reference sound pressure.

The user creates a description for each FW-H surface to determine the acoustic pressure in the far field: name, type of analogy (Ffowcs Williams-Hawkings or Curle), formulation, interpolation scheme, and specifies the calculation parameters: start and end time, external pressure and density, location of microphones, reference sound pressure, etc.

The developed library based on OpenFOAM package is in open access [9] and can be compiled independently of any modules of the main package and the type of solvers.

3. Validation cases

3.1 Rod-airfoil

One of the benchmark tasks of computational aeroacoustics in the aviation industry is the calculation of the flow past a cylinder with airfoil NACA0012. This section shows the ability of the LES simulation

on the unstructured mesh to predict the noise generated by the rod-airfoil configuration. The near-field and the acoustic results have been compared with the experimental data [10].

3.1.1 Computational case and mesh

The main characteristic dimensions of the models and the flow parameters in a numerical simulation correspond to the experimental conditions. So a NACA0012 airfoil with chord $C = 0.1\text{m}$ was set one chord downstream of a cylindrical rod with a diameter of $d = 0.1\text{C}$. The inlet velocity field was equal to $U_0 = 72\text{m/s}$. The Reynold number based on the rod diameter was $Re_d = 4.8 \cdot 10^4$.

The computational domain was discretized using snappyHexMesh utility. The general scheme of the boundary conditions and sizes of the computation domain is shown in Fig. 1(a). The feature of the calculation grid is the presence of refinement zones near the cylinder, profile and downstream. The domain was extended for $3d = 0.03\text{m}$ ($30d$ in experiment) in spanwise direction. The total 3D computational mesh size was about $9 \cdot 10^6$ cells. Fragment of the mesh and location of the FW-H surface is shown in Fig 1(b).

Figure 1: Domain parameters: (a) boundary conditions; (b) mesh configuration and FW-H surface.

The GT formulation has been used to predict acoustic noise in the far field. Virtual microphones were located at a distance of $R = 1.85\text{m}$ from the airfoil centre (half chord), the microphone's position angle θ was equal to 60° to 120° degrees.

The pisoFoam solver and LES approach with Smagorinsky subgrid turbulence model were used for unsteady turbulent flow simulation. This solver uses the PISO algorithm to connect the equation of the velocity field and pressure. The filteredLinearM scheme proposed in the papers [11,12] has been used for discretization of convective term. The time step was $dt = 8 \cdot 10^{-7}$ seconds and the Courant number does not exceed 0.2. The data sampling on the FW-H surface was done every 5 time step after convergence of the flow.

3.1.2 Near-field results

The vortex shedding behind the rod is plotted in Fig. 2. In this case, the boundary layer on the rod is laminar, the transition to turbulence occurs in the wake, and instability waves occur in the shear layers. Figure 3 shows a comparison between numerical and experimental results for profiles of the mean streamwise velocity for different cut sections: A1 ($x/C = -0.255$); A2 ($x/C = 0.25$); A3 ($x/C = 1.1$) (Fig.1a).

Figure 2: Instantaneous contours of Q-criteria (the color gradation on iso-surfaces shows the magnitude of velocity).

Figure 3: Mean streamwise velocity at different cut sections: (a) A1; (b) A2 (c) A3.

The vortex shedding by the rod interacts with the airfoil leading-edge. Large vortices are impinging directly the leading-edge. These interactions result in unsteady loads on the airfoil and in a modification of the acoustic spectrum.

3.1.3 Acoustic far field results

For comparison with the experimental data, it is necessary to make a correction of the results obtained, because the span of the experimental models was $30d$. The method of acoustic noise estimation in the far field for high span bodies was detail described in [13,14]. The results of acoustic noise calculation in the far field for the angle $\theta = 90^\circ$ and the value of its correction are given in Fig. 4(a). The far field directivity of the main peak is plotted in Fig. 4(b). The peak of SPL values is reached at $St = 0.192$ and frequency $f = 1385$ Hz. The received values coincide with the experimental data satisfactorily.

Figure 4: Acoustic properties: (a) acoustic PSD spectra at $\theta = 90^\circ$; (b) OASPL directivity

3.2 Jet flow at Low Reynolds Number

The spatial structure of the transonic jets is featured by small-scale and large-scale vortex structures, which leads to instability waves and acoustic noise generation. Therefore, numerical simulation of jet flow and the determination of acoustic perturbations generated by them is very difficult. In turn, the parameters of jet flow at small Reynolds numbers were well studied [15,16] and can be used to validate the numerical method and schemes.

3.2.1 Computational setup

The problem of transonic jet flow at low Reynolds number with the following initial data has been considered: exit diameter $D = 0.0079\text{m}$, exit velocity $U_j = 286\text{ m/s}$, exit temperature $T_j = 256\text{K}$, $n = p_a/p_\infty = 1$, $M_j = 0.9$, $Re_D = 3600$. The distribution of the velocity by diameter of nozzle exit is set as follows:

$$U(r) = 0.5 \cdot U_j \cdot \left[1 + \tanh \left(10 \cdot \left(1 - \frac{2r}{D} \right) \right) \right]. \quad (3)$$

The research of convergence of the solution depending on the grid resolution, numerical schemes and the solvers realized in the OpenFOAM package were conducted in works [17,18]. It was established that for numerical simulation of the jet flow at low Reynolds numbers the minimum grid size is $D/30$ - $D/40$. In this case, the computational domain was a rectangular parallelepiped with length $100D$, width and height $40D$. In addition, the calculation grid was refined along the jet axis by a distance of $30D$. The mesh size in this area was $D/40$ meters. The total number of cells was $30 \cdot 10^6$.

For numerical simulation pimpleCentralFoam solver with vanLeer scheme has been used. This solver based on the hybrid method of approximation of convective compounds and the Kurganov-Tadmor scheme [19]. The turbulence model was not applied.

3.2.2 Near-field results

Figure 5 presents the distribution of the mean Mach number in comparison with experimental data [15]. Figure 6 shows the jet flow structure obtained using the pimpleCentralFoam solver and vanLeer scheme. The color gradation on iso-surfaces shows the magnitude of velocity. Unsteady turbulent flow leads to acoustic perturbations.

Figure 5: Mean Mach number profiles: (a) $x/D = 1$; (b) $x/D = 5$; (c) axial distribution

Figure 6: Instantaneous contours of Q-criteria.

3.2.3 Acoustic far field results

The Farassat 1A formulation has been used to determine acoustic perturbations. Virtual microphones were located at a distance $R=30D$, the angle of the microphone's position θ was set from 15° to 90° degrees respectively. Two surfaces were constructed for the definition of acoustic noise, which are shown in Fig. 7 (S1 - red, S2 - green). The control surfaces start $0.1D$ downstream of the inflow boundary and extend to $35D$ along the streamwise direction.

Figure 7: Schematic showing the two open control surfaces surrounding the jet flow (vorticity of velocity are shown).

Figure 8 shows the results of OASPL calculation for two control surfaces in comparison with experimental data [15].

Figure 8: Overall sound pressure level directivity on an arc at 30D.

The obtained results of averaged and pulsation parameters of the jet correspond to the experimental data and calculations of other authors.

4. Conclusions

Validation of developed open-source library libAcoustics on the example of acoustic noise calculations for two benchmark problems with the use of different approaches to calculate the Ffowcs Williams and Hawkings equation is performed. The comparison of the obtained mean flow parameters and acoustic perturbations with the available experimental data has been carried out. The satisfactory coincidence of the obtained results with the experimental data allows to speak about the possibility to use the developed library based on the OpenFOAM package to solve a wide range of computational aeroacoustics tasks.

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